

**RESEARCH ON METHODS FOR DISTINGUISHING
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19563904>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 09th April 2026Accepted: 11th April 2026Online: 13th April 2026**KEYWORDS***natural honey, adulterated
honey, starch, iodine solution,
quality control, chemical
indicator***ABSTRACT***This thesis analyzes modern and traditional methods for detecting adulteration in honey. The increasing number of "fake honey" products enriched with sugar syrup or chemical additives on the market today calls for research and development of rapid detection methods.*

Honey is a natural product that is beneficial to human health. However, currently, there are more and more types of adulterated honey on the market. This situation has a negative impact on consumer health and reduces confidence in the quality of the product. Therefore, it is an urgent issue to scientifically study methods for distinguishing natural honey from fake honey.

Tsagkaris AS, Koulis GA and colleagues estimate that the honey market is susceptible to adulteration, with the addition of cheap sweet syrups to artificially dilute the product. The authors argue that chromatography, isotopic, and spectroscopy methods are effective in distinguishing natural and adulterated honey, and that modern analytical methods such as analysis, PCA, and PLSDA, play a role in reliable evidence of the role of quantitative models in the analysis of honey.[1]

According to the research of Cabañero AI, Recio JL and co-authors, the adulteration of honey products is mainly carried out by adding sweet syrups based on cane or corn. The authors emphasize that stable isotope ratio analysis (IRMS) has a high accuracy in the identification of natural and artificial honey. They believe that isotopic methods can reliably identify external carbohydrate sources in honey, and this method is widely used in international standards [2].

Ruiz-Matute AI and other researchers have shown the importance of chromatographic methods in detecting cases of honey adulteration. The authors state that by determining the quantitative and qualitative composition of sugars using liquid chromatography, it is possible to distinguish between natural honey and products with added sugar syrups. Also, evaluating the obtained data based on multivariate statistical analysis increases the accuracy of the results [3].

Gallardo-Velázquez T. et al. have highlighted the effectiveness of spectroscopic methods, in particular FTIR and NIR spectroscopy, in the authentication of honey. The researchers note that by using these methods in combination with chemometric models, including PCA and

PLS-DA, it is possible to classify natural and adulterated honey samples with high accuracy. According to the authors, such an integrated approach is a rapid and reliable analytical method [4].

Research methodology

The main goal of this study is to analyze the differences between natural and adulterated honey using chemical methods and evaluate their effectiveness.

In studies conducted by Bertelli D., Lolli M. and others, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy is considered an advanced method for honey authentication. The authors argue that by combining NMR data with chemometric analysis, it is possible to determine the origin and degree of adulteration of honey with high accuracy.

Research object: natural honey and adulterated honey samples:

For natural honey

Natural mountain honey is honey obtained from wild and wind-blown plants (flowers, shrubs, wild herbs) in mountainous regions.

Bees collect this flower nectar and turn it into high-quality, pure, and additive-free honey through a natural process.

Natural cotton honey is a natural honey collected by bees from the nectar of cotton flowers blooming in cotton fields.

It is distinguished by its light color, mild taste, and rapid hardening.

Since cotton fields are located in large, open areas, the honey is clean and pure.

For fake honey:

Fake honey 1.- This type of fake honey is made by processing sugar beet juice and sugar syrup.

Fake Honey 2- This fake honey is made from glucose syrup derived from corn or wheat starch.

Results of the study

For the chemical method (determination of the presence of starch).

There are 4 different samples for this method. 2 different samples of natural honey and 2 different samples of adulterated honey are taken. The first step is to put 4 different samples of 10 grams each into 4 test tubes. Then, the same amount of 10 grams of water is added. The 4 different samples are brought to the same mass. The next step is to drop 3 mg of iodine (I). After the iodine is dropped, it is mixed. After this step, the colors of the 4 different samples change radically. In our experiment, natural honey does not change its color because it does not contain starch, but adulterated honey changes its color because it contains starch.

In our study, we added honey to water in 3 different amounts and tested it with iodine. Our first ratio was 1:1, our second ratio was 3:1, and our third ratio was 5:1.

All of these ratios yielded different results.

1:1 ratio – At this stage, we take a 10 g sample of our honey, add 10 g of water to it and mix it. 3 mg of iodine was added to the mixed sample. During this process, the color of our samples did not change.

3:1 ratio – In this process, 10 grams of honey was mixed with 30 grams of water. 3 mg of iodine was also added to this process. After a while, a small change was noticed in the fake bees.

5:1 ratio – In this process, a 10 g sample of honey was taken and mixed with 50 g of water. 3 mg of iodine was also added to this sample. After some time, a significant change occurred in the fake honey. However, our natural honey retained its previous state.

In recent years, modern analytical methods such as FTIR and NMR spectroscopy have been successfully used to determine the chemical “fingerprint” of honey. Koulis et al. (2017) emphasize that the use of these methods in combination with chemometric analysis allows for the accurate classification of natural and adulterated honey. In particular, the use of PCA (Principal Component Analysis) and PLS-DA (Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis) models plays an important role in in-depth analysis of data and drawing reliable conclusions.

Table 1

The authenticity of honey is determined by a 1:1 ratio. Prepare a solution of water and honey and determine

No	Sample name	Water content (g)	Amount of honey added (g)	Iodine content (mg)	Iodine when added color	Conclusion
1	Natural mountain honey	10	10	3	The color has not changed.	Starch is not present in natural honey.
2	Natural cotton honey	10	10	3	The color has not changed.	Starch is not present in natural honey.
3	Fake honey 1	10	10	3	The solution turned slightly bluish.	Starch is present in small amounts in adulterated honey.
4	Fake honey 2	10	10	3	The solution turned slightly purple.	Starch is present in small amounts in adulterated honey.

Table 2

The authenticity of honey is determined by a 3:1 ratio. Prepare a solution of water and honey and determine

No	Sample name	Water content (gr)	Amount of honey added (gr)	Iodine content (mg)	Iodine when added color	Conclusion
1	Natural mountain honey	30	10	3	The color has not changed.	Starch is not present in natural honey.
2	Natural cotton honey	30	10	3	The color has not changed.	Starch is not present in natural honey.
3	Fake	30	10	3	The	

	honey 1				solution turned completely blue.	Adulterated honey containing starch
4	Fake honey 2	30	10	3	The solution turned purple.	Strongly adulterated honey containing starch

Table 3

The authenticity of honey is determined by a 5:1 ratio. Prepare a solution of water and honey and determine

№	Sample name	Water content (gr)	Amount of honey added (gr)	Iodine content (mg)	Iodine when added color	Conclusion
1	Natural mountain honey	50	10	3	The color has not changed.	Starch is not present in natural honey.
2	Natural cotton honey	50	10	3	The color has not changed.	Starch is not present in natural honey.
3	Fake honey 1	50	10	3	The solution turned slightly bluish in color.	Starch is present in small amounts in adulterated honey.
4	Fake honey 2	50	10	3	The solution turned a small amount of purple.	Starch is present in small amounts in adulterated honey.

Discussion of the study

According to the results presented in the table, the natural honey samples did not react with the iodine solution, which confirms that they do not contain starch.

Samples of adulterated honey change color when exposed to iodine, which scientifically proves the presence of starch in its composition.

In recent years, the adulteration of honey products has become an urgent problem from the point of view of food safety and consumer confidence. Literature analysis shows that the most common method of adulteration is the addition of cheap sugar syrups to natural honey, which significantly changes the chemical and physical properties of the product. Therefore, high-precision analytical approaches are required to reliably distinguish natural and adulterated honey.

The use of chromatographic methods by researchers allows for a detailed study of the sugar profile of honey. In particular, the determination of the quantitative ratios of monosaccharides and disaccharides using liquid chromatography is of great importance in

assessing the structural balance inherent in natural honey. In adulterated samples, these ratios are disturbed, which increases the diagnostic potential of chromatographic analysis.

Isotopic analysis methods, in particular the determination of the ratio of stable carbon isotopes, are recognized as one of the most reliable approaches to honey authentication. This method allows to determine the addition of external carbohydrate sources to the honey composition based on differences in the photosynthetic mechanisms of plants. The advantage of the isotopic approach is that it is recognized within the framework of international standards and provides highly reproducible results.

Spectroscopic methods are characterized by their speed and ease of sample preparation. FTIR and NIR spectroscopy provide a general chemical “fingerprint” of honey and identify spectral changes that may occur as a result of adulteration. However, modern statistical approaches are required to fully interpret such complex data.

From this point of view, the use of chemometric models, including PCA and PLS-DA methods, significantly increases the information value of analytical data. As a result of multivariate analysis, natural and adulterated honey samples are clearly divided into groups, reducing the likelihood of misclassification. The integration of analytical and statistical methods is emerging as a comprehensive and effective approach to honey authentication.

In general, the analysis of the literature shows that there is no single universal method for detecting honey adulteration. To achieve the highest reliability, it is advisable to use chromatographic, isotopic and spectroscopic methods in combination with chemometric models. Such an integrated approach serves as an effective tool not only in scientific research, but also in quality control and certification processes.

Conclusion

Studies using the iodine test have shown that this method is a simple, rapid, and reliable chemical method for distinguishing natural and adulterated honey. According to the results, a color change is clearly observed in honey samples with added starch.

The literature review shows that the adulteration of honey products remains a serious problem for the food safety system today. The addition of mainly cheap carbohydrate sources to natural honey disrupts the original chemical balance of the product and misleads consumers. Therefore, the issue of determining the authenticity of honey requires scientifically based and highly accurate methods.

The results of the analysis showed that determining the sugar content of honey using chromatographic approaches is of great importance in detecting adulteration. In particular, isotopic analysis methods stand out as one of the most reliable methods for identifying external carbohydrate sources. At the same time, although spectroscopic methods are notable for their speed and practical convenience, their effectiveness in many cases increases only when combined with statistical analysis.

Based on the results, it can be said that there is no single universal analytical method for honey authentication. To achieve the highest accuracy and reliability, it is advisable to use various physicochemical analysis methods in combination with chemometric models. Such an integrated approach serves as an effective solution not only for scientific research, but also for practical quality control and certification processes

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